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Ground motion detection in Central South Asturias (N Spain) by using Sentinel-1 SAR data

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In this work, the A-DInSAR techniques are applied in a mountainous area located in the Central South of Asturias (N Spain), where there are significant landslide and subsidence phenomena. The main aim of this study is detecting and analysing ground deformations associated to slope instabilities and subsidence processes. For this, 113 SAR images, provided by Sentinel-1A/B between January 2018 and February 2020, were acquired and processed by means of PSIG software (developed by the Geomatics Division of the CTTC). The results show a velocity range between -18.4 and 10.0 mm/year, and minimum and maximum accumulated ground displacements of -35.0 and 17.5 mm. This study has made possible to differentiate local sectors with recent deformation related to landslide incidence, urban/mining subsidence, and land recuperation due to aquifer recharge. This work corroborates the reliability and usefulness of the A-DInSAR processing as a powerful tool in the study and analysis of geological hazards on regional and local scales using Sentinel-1 data collection, showing also the high difficulty of processing mountainous areas with few urban sectors.